

COGNITIVE-SEMANTIC SPECIFICITY OF LEXICAL UNIT VERBALIZING THE CONCEPT OF "A PERSON" IN THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

The article presents the investigation of the concept "person" in the English language. The research is based on semantic and conceptual analysis of the lexeme "person" in English. The semantic analysis shows that the traditional classification of semantic components has to be adapted to the specific features of the lexemes and it should include integrative, distinguishing, opposing, relevant and implicit components.

Cognitive linguistics is a direction that focuses on language as a general cognitive mechanism and that part of knowledge about language that considers the interaction of the level of meanings and concepts that exist in our minds [5]. Linguistic thinking is accompanied by a mechanism of internal translation of information from the level of concepts to the level of meanings, and vice versa.

The presence of a universal conceptual level ensures the success of translation from one language into another language with different systems of meanings or allows you to discover the connection between the code concepts of language memory and predetermines the vision of the world of a certain era.

Cognitive linguistics uses the terms categorization, conceptualization, picture of the world, concept, concept sphere, conceptual model, conceptual metaphor, conceptual feature. [4]. The approval of these terms in linguistics marked a new stage in the comprehension of the ways, patterns of interaction between language, consciousness and culture, and, consequently, new aspects of the interaction of linguistics, cognitive science, cultural studies, philosophy, expanded the scope of a meaningful analysis of linguistic phenomena.

The actualization of the anthropological orientation of the new phenomenon in the language is largely due to the fact that the word is focused not only on the thing, but also on its perception. Man again becomes the measure of all things, so the interest of linguists has shifted from describing the internal structure of the language to the conditions of its use. The new scientific paradigm in linguistics is an anthropocentric paradigm, the focus of which is "man in language" and "language in man", the main problem is the interaction of man, culture and language.[5].

One of the urgent problems of modern cognitive linguistics is to compare the key concepts of different cultures in terms of the distribution of features and their further

structuring in the semantic spaces of lexemes that serve to objectify concepts in the linguistic worldviews.

The concept in this work is interpreted as a unit of cognition, which is a mental structure fixed by collective experience, which includes the sum of the main characteristics of the referent, the assessment of these characteristics, as well as the sum of relations to the referent. Unlike meaning, which is also a mental formation, it is in the concept that the potential for change lies, since the meaning is single and situational and relates to the concept as a single to a general one.

The purpose of this work is to describe and study the concept of "person" from the point of view of cognitive-semantics, as well as to analyze the allocation of common and specific components expressed in this concept in the languages under study.

In English, there are two lexemes for denoting a person - man and human. Thus, the concept "person" in English contains two key lexemes, which are somewhat different in their meaning, expressing the originality of this concept in the language. Previously, the human lexeme was widely used in oral colloquial speech, literature, and folklore and was perceived as the opposition of man as an earthly being to the gods.

In modern English, the human lexeme is used mainly in scientific texts that consider a person as a biological type, that is, the human lexeme implies consideration of a person in the aspect of physicality. In colloquial speech and other types of texts, human is replaced by the lexeme man.[4].

The concept of man in English is presented as an image of a subject who has the qualities that are attributed to him by society, and a certain degree of power, a person who performs a certain type of work within the laws of society.[3].

Based on the results of the study, it seems possible to define the concept of "man" as an image of a member of society with external characteristics and internal qualities, which is conceived as an activity subject, building its activity on moral laws and occupying a certain place in the social hierarchy.[2].

The study of the seme composition of the values of the selected units allows us to speak about the need to use a classification of features that differs from the generally accepted one (cf. the analysis of the concepts "personality" and "person" carried out by R.I. Rozina [6]).

The scheme adopted by us is as follows:

- an integrating feature, including the concretizing feature of the seme;
- distinguishing features for each unit;
- opposing signs, "highlighting" those semes that a given unit cannot have (shown with a "-" sign);
- irrelevant features that are never implemented in contexts;
- implicit signs.

At first glance, the semantic structures of these two units are almost the same. However, the analysis of contexts and their translation show that the seme "male" is much more pronounced in the English unit, even in the meaning of "homo sapiens". So, for the word "man", the corpus of compatibility includes adjectives good, kind, sad, cheerful, honest, smart, stupid, businesslike, hardworking, [not] tall, strong, weak, healthy, sick, influential, rich. Among other models of compatibility: a person of some height, some years; a man of

deeds, words, without his own opinion, without conscience, with some kind of face, with some eyes, with some hair [about what kind of person]; know, respect person, believe (believe) in smth. person to do (to do) smth. for some person, to apologize (apologize) to smth. human [1].

The integrating feature for each series is the feature "man", or "homo sapiens", which, in turn, is decomposed into a number of concretizing semes.

So, cross-linguistic analysis showed the dynamics of the development of the concept "person" in the English language picture of the world and its reflection on the semantics of language units, aimed at penetrating especially those values and relations that manifest themselves as attitudes in the cultural-conceptual picture of the world of the people - native speaker.

Conclusion. The concept of person in the English language has two lexemes which are human and man. Both of them reflects humanbeings but differs in its semantics. Cognitive-semantic analysis of the concept person presented distinguishing features of lexemes denoting to person. Also, the article presented some adjectives denoting to a person.

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